

influenced by puddling treatment (see table). Plots puddled with the rotary power tiller and the iron puddler had significantly higher yields than those puddled with the iron plow and the wooden puddler. Yields with the rotary power tiller, iron puddler, and country wooden plow and with the wooden plow, the iron plow, and the wooden puddler were similar. Yields with all implements increased across the 3 yr. □

Effect of puddling implement on rice grain yield. Maharashtra, India, 1982-84.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)					CD (0.05)
	Rotary power tiller	Iron puddler	Iron plow	Country wooden plow	Wooden puddler	
1982	2.2	2.3	2.0	2.0	2.4	ns
1983	3.5	3.4	2.7	2.8	2.4	0.48
1984	5.0	4.7	4.5	5.0	4.5	ns
Pooled mean	3.6	3.5	3.0	3.3	3.1	0.34

Effect of sodicity and pretransplanting submergence on rice yield

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We evaluated the effect on yield of four percentages of exchangeable sodium (ESP) and length of pretransplanting submergence. The split-plot design had ESP levels in the main plots and pretransplanting submergence in the subplots, with four replications. Subplot was 40 m². Urea at 150 kg N/ha and 9 kg Zn/ha were applied: half the N and all the Zn at transplanting and half the N topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. The crop was harvested 1 Nov 1982.

Presubmergence for 15 and 30 d increased yields (see figure). This effect was more pronounced at high ESP. The mean yield increase due to 15 d

Effect of sodicity and pretransplanting submergence on rice yield. Karnal, India, 1982.

Change in soil pH, ESP, and exchangeable Ca + Mg after rice harvest. Karnal, India, 1982.

Soil no.	Before rice			After rice		
	ESP	pH	Exchangeable Ca + Mg (meq/100 g)	ESP	pH	Exchangeable Ca + Mg (meq/100 g)
1	82	10.2	1.4	70	9.8	2.1
2	72	9.9	2.1	58	9.5	3.1
3	65	9.7	2.8	47	9.4	3.8
4	35	9.3	5.2	25	9.0	6.0

submergence was 0.5 t/ha and that to 30 d submergence, 0.9 t/ha.

The effect was beneficial because these sodic soils undergo reduction in pH and redox potential, increase in partial pressure of CO₂ (PCO₂), and change in other physicochemical characteristics within 2 wk of flooding. This creates a favorable ionic

environment in the rhizosphere.

Seedlings transplanted immediately after flooding (0 day presubmergence) showed stunted growth and lower yields because of initially high pH and ESP and reduced availability of nutrients. ESP and pH of the soils decreased substantially after rice under flooded conditions (see table). □

Effect of seeding date and seedling age on dry season yield

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Assured canal irrigation and improved marketing have led to dry season rice cultivation in South Gujarat. Information is needed on optimum seeding date and seedling age at transplanting for summer cultivation of long-duration variety Mahsuri.

We conducted a field experiment on the college farm during 1981-82 and 1982-83 summer seasons. The split-plot design had 4 seeding dates (1 Nov, 15 Nov, 30 Nov, and 15 Dec) as main plot treatments and 3 seedling ages (45,

55, and 65 d old) as subplot treatments. There were four replications. The crop was fertilized with 100 kg N and 22 kg P/ha. All the P and half the N were basally applied at transplanting, the

Interaction effect of seeding date and seedling age at transplanting on grain yield of Mahsuri rice.^a Gujarat, India, 1981-82, 1982-1983 summer seasons.

Seeding date	Grain yield (t/ha) by seedling age		
	45 d	55 d	65 d
1 Nov	3.7	3.9	4.2
15 Nov	3.9	4.4	4.1
30 Nov	5.3	6.2	3.9
15 Dec	4.4	4.1	3.3
CD (0.05)	0.2		

^aPooled data for 2 summer seasons.